

THE INFLUENCE OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT ON ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed to find out the influence of academic achievement, gender and their interaction on achievement motivation of secondary school students. Survey method was conducted on a random sample of 200 (153 boys and 47 girls) secondary students of Bareilly district. Achievement Motivation Test (ACMT) developed by Dr. V. P. Bhargava (2009) was used for measuring Achievement motivation and High school marks of students were used for academic achievement. Data were analyzed with the help of two way ANOVA and t-test. Findings showed that high academic achiever had high achievement motivation than low and moderate academic achiever. Findings also indicated that there is no significant difference in achievement motivation and academic achievement of male and female students. It also revealed that there is no significant influence of interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation.

KEYWORDS: Academic achievement, achievement motivation, secondary school students.

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental aim of motivation is to stimulate and to facilitate learning activity. Learning is an active process that needs to be motivated and guided toward desirable ends. The effectiveness of learning depends in part upon the strength of the needs and upon the satisfaction the learning brings. It can be said that the rate of learning depends upon the strength of the motive. So we can say that motivation is the very heart of the learning process. It has significant role in student's academic life. Motivation refers to the behaviour

of an individual who strives to accomplish something to do this best and to excel others performance. This involves Competition with a particular standard of excellence of performance. Researchers often find a strong correlation between motivation to learn and student achievement (Wang and others, 1993).

Achievement motivation is the basic need for success or the attainment of excellence. Achievement motivation can be understood simply as the tendency to strive for success or the attainment of a desired goal. The importance of achievement motivation in the learning and achievement process has been given a great deal of attention in the recent researches. Individuals will satisfy their needs through different means, and are driven to succeed for varying reasons both internal and external. According to McClelland (1985), Achievement motivation has been defined as the extent to which individuals differ in their need to strive to attain rewards, such as physical satisfaction, praise from others and feelings of personal mastery.

Achievement Motivation provides a means of powerful and higher aim in the life of the students. As a human concept, Achievement Motivation involves creativity in the discovery of patterns of learning and reaching the goal. Therefore, it is one of the essential areas of learning. Everyone needs to develop Achievement Motivational concepts and skills; this would help them to understand and motivate in learning that would also help them to achieve their goal. In education achievement motivation aims to provide students understanding with their right motive to achieve the goal. Achievement Motivation is a conception that is not commonly use. It is guidelines to our behavior. It is the abstract goal which people seek to achieve.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Awan, et al. (2011), Meijer et al. (2004) and Emmanuel et al. (2014) investigated that achievement motivation is significantly related to academic achievement. Chetri (2014) found a positive significantly correlation between achievement motivation and academic achievement. Nagarathanamma & Rao (2007) and Pawar (2017) found no significant

difference between boys and girls with regard to achievement motivation level (Chetri, 2014), while Adsul *et al.* (2008) investigated the effects of gender differences on achievement motivation, male students were found to be having a high achievement motivation while female students having a below average level of achievement motivation. Santha & Chamundeswari (2015) investigated that girls are significantly better than the boys in matriculation and central board schools at the secondary level with respect to their achievement motivation and academic achievement.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

According to the quoted research review, the achievement motivation plays an important role in predicting students' future success. Therefore, it is crucial to put special emphasis on forming high level of students' need for achievement through special training programs and proper guidance. Achievement motivation is one of the crucial psychological factors determining future academic and occupational success. At the secondary level students should be selected the groups and subjects of their own interest. The researcher feels that this study will highlight the role of achievement motivation for one's life.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the influence of academic achievement on achievement motivation of secondary school students.
2. To study the differences on achievement motivation of male and female students with respect to their academic achievement.
3. To study the influence of interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation of secondary students.
4. To study the differences of academic achievement of male and female students.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1. There is no significant difference among higher, moderate and lower academic achiever on achievement motivation of secondary school students.

- H2. There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of male and female students.
- H3. There is no significant influence of interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation of secondary school students.
- H4. There is no significant difference of academic achievement of male and female students.

METHODOLOGY

The casual comparative design of descriptive research has been adopted for this study. The secondary school students of Bareilly district affiliated to UP board constitute the population. The sample of the present study was drawn from ten schools through random sampling technique. The total sample of the students was 200 consisting of 153 boys and 47 girls. Achievement Motivation Test (ACMT) developed by Dr. V. P. Bhargava (2009) was used for Achievement motivation and High school marks of students were used for academic achievement. The data collected from the sample was analyzed by using two way ANOVA and t-test. The study was delimited to secondary students affiliated to U.P. Board of Bareilly district only.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis of data, interpretation and discussion of the results are presented below:

Descriptive Statistics of Achievement motivation

	Achievement Motivation	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Academic Achievement	High	Male	24.22	4.63	37
		Female	27.13	4.76	15
		Total	25.06	4.81	52
	Moderate	Male	21.16	4.42	76
		Female	19.88	5.91	17
		Total	20.92	4.72	93
	Low	Male	19.83	3.86	40
		Female	20.67	4.42	15

		Total	20.05	4.00	55
	Total	Male	21.55	4.60	153
		Female	22.45	5.97	47
		Total	21.76	4.95	20

(1) Analysis of main effect of academic achievement, student's gender and their interaction on achievement motivation.

Table-1: Summary of Analysis of Variance of Achievement Motivation

Sources of Variance	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F- Ratio
Academic achievement	2	832.46	416.23	20.33**
Gender	1	23.96	23.96	1.17
Academic Achievement*Gender	2	106.76	53.38	2.61
Error	194	3970.98	20.47	

**Significant at 0.01 Significance level

H1. There is no significant difference among higher, moderate and lower academic achiever on achievement motivation of secondary school students.

From above table 1, it is revealed that F-value (20.33) is found to be highly significant at .01 significance level for df (2,194) for main effect of academic achievement. So, assertion made by null hypothesis (H1) that 'there is no significant difference among higher, moderate and lower academic achiever on achievement motivation of secondary school students' is rejected. It refers that level of academic achievement affect the achievement motivation of students significantly. Findings reveal that with high academic achievement had high achievement motivation than low and moderate academic achievers.

H2. There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of male and female students.

From above table 1, On the contrary to it, F-value (1.17) for main effect of gender on achievement motivation is found to be non significant at .05 significance level for df (1,194). It denotes that gender of students does not affect their achievement motivation significantly. So, null hypothesis (H2) that ‘there is no significant difference of achievement motivation of male and female students’ is accepted.

H3. There is no significant influence of interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation of secondary school students.

From above table 1, F-value (2.61) is found to be non significant at .05 significance level for df (2,194). Hence, null hypothesis (H3) that ‘there is no significant influence of interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation of secondary school students’ is accepted.

The fact, F-value for the interaction between level of academic achievement and gender is not found significant, it indicates that the difference between the means of male and female students in the high, moderate and low academic group do not differ significantly from one another. With a non significant interaction effect between academic achievement and gender, it may be said that main effect due to level of academic achievement i.e., significant difference among the mean of achievement motivation for higher, moderate and lower academic achievement group of students, is independent of the effect of gender.

Fig. 1. Mean scores of Achievement motivation of secondary school students due to high, moderate and low academic achiever

Fig. 2. Interaction between academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation

Table-2: Comparison of academic achievement between male and female students

Categories	N	Mean	S.D.	t-Ratio
Male	153	68.60	8.28	-0.52
Female	47	69.32	8.02	

*Significant at 0.05 Significance level

H4. There is no significant difference of academic achievement of male and female students.

From table-2, the mean score of academic achievement of male and female students did not significant at .05 level of significance for df (198). So the null hypothesis, ‘there is no significant difference of academic achievement of male and female students’ as accepted. The mean score of academic achievement of female students (M=69.32) was found to be

higher than the mean score of male students ($M=68.60$). Female students have more attention on their study than male students, but this difference was not significant.

Fig. 3. Mean scores of academic achievement of male and female students

SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

The following was the main findings of the present study-

1. The level of academic achievement affects the achievement motivation of students.
2. Gender of students does not affect their achievement motivation.
3. The interaction affect between level of academic achievement and gender on achievement motivation to be not significant.
4. Male and female students did not differ on their academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that high academic achiever students had high level of achievement motivation for their future achievement and success, and lower academic achiever students had low level of achievement motivation. Male and female students did not differ on their achievement motivation and academic achievement. it shows that gender did not affect achievement motivation and academic performance of students. It is also concluded that interaction between academic achievement and gender did not affect their achievement motivation of students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

At the secondary level students should select the streams and subjects of their own interest. Academic counselors should organize guidance programs such as workshops, symposia and public lectures periodically for students to equipped them to enhance their academic performance and achievement motivation. Teachers and parents should be focus on intrinsic motivation which will have greater affect on students' performance. Curriculum developers should design programmes and courses that will motivate students to think critically and to enhance their achievement motivation. Quiz competitions, class presentations and inter school debates should be organized for students to enhance their achievement motivation.

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